

Water modelling system upgrade and software support services

Final report

Client: Lithuanian Environmental protection agency

Agreement # 28T-2020-43 of 04-Aug-2020

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Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs

SUMMARY

The final report provides the description of activities done and results obtained within the project lifetime. Specifically, the report describes activities and results in the time period following the acceptance of the 2nd interim report. These include training of the Agency's personnel, application of the SWAT Check software, improvement of the modelling system, complementing and testing the script library.

Report is written in English, it contains 68 pages, 56 figures, 7 tables and 5 references.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This is the final report in the framework of the Contract #28T-2020-43 of 04-Aug-2020 between the Lithuanian Environmental protection agency (Client) and “SIA Procesu analizēs un izpētes centrs” (Consultant). According to the Contract the final report is prepared within 24 months from the starting date of the Contract (22-Sep-2020).

The aim of the project is the upgrade of the SWAT water quantity and quality modelling system of Lithuania and providing the related software support services, i.e. operational support during the initial phase of the application of the updated system.

As such, the project is divided into 3 stages:

- The first stage (Sep/2020-Mar/2021) is the upgrade of the modelling system and renewal of its input data.
- The second stage (Mar/2021-Sep/2021) is the calibration of the upgraded modelling system and development of an extensive script library for its usage. The maturity of the SWAT+ modelling system by the end of 2021 was found inadequate to reach the project aims in respect the modelling of water quality; therefore the final revision of the 2nd Interim report marking the ecnd of Stage II was postponed to early July 2022.
- The third stage (Sep/2021-Sep/2022) is the support of the upgraded modelling system and its software elements.

According to the Contract the inception report PAIC (2020) described the planned activities and timing for the implementation of the project activities; it included agreed modifications of the Terms of reference of the project. The reference to the paragraph numbers in this modified ToR PAIC (2020) is used throughout the final report.

The results of the first stage were submitted in the 1st Interim report PAIC (2021). It included

1. The renewal – change of the background technologies – of the modelling system, moving from Python 2 to Python 3, SWAT2012 to the SWAT+ and transfer of the ArcGIS GIS functions to the open source GIS libraries (ToR 1.1).
2. The upgrade of the data of the modelling system: the spatial division - river network and respective basin data (ToR 2.1) and of the rest of the modelling system input data (ToR 2.2).
3. Adding of new functionality – ability to model small water bodies – to the modelling system (ToR 1.2) and adding rainfall radar data as a precipitation input data to the model (ToR 1.3).
4. The results of the 1st stage (preprocessed data, geodatabases, program code, SWAT+ setups) were prepared and submitted in the electronic format.

The results of the 2nd stage were presented in the 2nd Interim report PAIC (2022). These results included the following parts:

1. The updating and recalibrating of the Modeling system prepared with new, updated data and the newest SWAT+ model revision version (ToR 2.4). It includes preparatory steps and recalibration plan (ToR 2.4.1-2.4.6), description of the course of recalibration and its results (ToR 2.4.7) and comparison of the calibrated Agency's SWAT2012 and updated SWAT+ Modeling systems (ToR 2.4.8).
2. Development and description of a comprehensive library of scripts. It included the scripts for (a) the automatic preparation of the Modeling system for the modeling application of pollution abatement measures or introduction of new pollution sources and automatic extraction of modeling results (ToR 1.4) and (b) scripts for HELCOM PLC data extraction from Modeling system (ToR 1.5)
3. The miscellaneous results including the description of tools created for the implementation of the project, as well as of the cloud service for versioning and delivery of the Modelling system (ToR 3.1).

Together with PAIC (2021, 2022) as well as with this report the project results (preprocessed data, geodatabases, program code, SWAT+ setups, SWAT+ modelling results) were prepared in electronic format and delivered in the cloud service.

This final report describes in detail the results obtained in the last stage of the project mainly focusing on implementation or study of additional functionality and consultation on technical problems working with the updated Modeling system (ToR 3.2). The report is organised as follows:

1. The additional studies carried out on a modelling system are described in Chapter 2:
 - a. investigation of application of SWAT+ Check in Section 2.1;
 - b. improvement of water quantity and quality modelling performance in particular watersheds in Section 2.2.
2. Several scripts are added to the comprehensive script library in Chapter 3 – namely, implementing land use change via decision tables, and script for introducing managed drainage via decision tables.
3. The additional study was performed to assess the reliability of the modelling system for the modelling of water quality improvement measures. The use of the scripts implementing various measures is tested in Chapter 4.
4. The additional studies carried out during the final stage led to fixing several additional bugs in SWAT+ source code. The list of such errors is provided in Chapter 5 as revision of the respective Chapter of PAIC (2022).
5. The acceptance of the 1st Interim report PAIC (2021) was conditional. The description of addressing these conditions is given in Chapter 6.

6. The training sessions for the Agencies personnel were performed in the last stage of the project. The training materials from these sessions are summarised in Chapter 7 complementing and upgrading the description of the modelling system already provided in PAIC (2022).

The cloud service for versioning and delivery of the Modelling system was delivered with PAIC (2022). However, this system does not meet the 2Tb criteria specified in ToR. Therefore, the Consultant has provided an additional 2Tb cloud drive with versioning and sync functionality for the Client which may be used for storing of the modelling results.

2. ADDITIONAL STUDIES ON MODELLING SYSTEM

2.1. SWAT+ CHECK

2.1.1. Introduction

Results of SWAT Check for updated Modeling system should be examined as well as differences between model results and monitoring averaged by months (seasonal differences) according to ToR 2.4.3. SWAT Check was not compatible with SWAT+ during the preparation of the 2nd Interim report in November 2021. The SWAT+ Check was included in SWAT+ Toolbox¹ in spring 2022, however, the development group indicates that it is in the development stage, for instance, it does not process water quality data. Therefore, SWAT Check was not considered in PAIC (2022). Client requested the SWAT+ Check Study to be performed in the final stage of the project. Its application to the calibrated modelling system is given throughout the Subsections of the Section 2.1.

2.1.2. Region AI

Hydrometric station Akmena-Dane-Kretinga was used for recalibration in western hydrological region AI. The results of SWAT+ Check for Akmena-Dane watershed are presented in Figure 1 for water quantity.

The single warning is related to warm-up period; in our modelling system we do not use the observations of the first modelling years for the calibration/validation.

Table 1: Comparison of water balance components by PAIC's scripts and SWAT+ Check.

Parameter	PAIC	SWAT+Check
PREC	867.94	867.34
ET	393.02	392.75
SURQ	115.11	115.03
LATQ	81.14	81.08
TILEQ	157.72	157.61
GW_Q	84.72	84.66

We checked the SWAT+ Check software via comparison with SWAT+ calculations of the water balance elements with the results produced of our script included in the modelling system. This comparison is given in Table 1. We conclude that SWAT+ Check is accurate for assessment of the water quantity part of the SWAT+ modelling system.

¹ <https://swat.tamu.edu/software/plus/>

Messages and Warnings

- It is highly recommended that you use at least 1 year of model warmup; 2-5 years is better

Water Balance Ratios

Streamflow/Precipitation	0.32
Baseflow/Total Flow	0.59
Surface Runoff/Total Flow	0.41
Percolation/Precipitation	0.13
Deep Recharge/Precipitation	0.01
ET/Precipitation	0.45

Figure 1: SWAT+ Check report for water quantity of Akmena-Dane watershed.

Water quality station Akmena-Danė-ties-Tūbausiai. was selected for recalibration in this hydrological region AI. The SWAT+ Check was applied for the water quality modelling results of the watershed of Akmena-Dane, see Figure 2 for nitrogen, and Figure 3 for phosphorus.

We conclude that SWAT+ Check is not compatible with SWAT+ modelling results for the part of water quality; several state variables of fluxes are indicated as zero or N/A in the SWAT+ Check output. These problems of SWAT+ Check are shown by red circles in Figures 2-3.

Figure 2: SWAT+ Check screenshot for Akmena-Dane. Nitrogen cycle and warnings.

Figure 3: SWAT+ Check screenshot for Akmena-Dane. Phosphorus cycle and warnings.

2.1.2. Region AII

Jūra catchment was used for recalibration in western region AII. The results of SWAT+ Check for Jūra watershed is presented in Figure 4 for water quantity.

The warnings of SWAT+ Check are the same as in PAIC&VUB (2014) where they are analyzed in more details. 2. In general, SWAT+ considers problematic a large portion of lateral flow. However, comparing to the amount of the water which is available in tile drainage flow, this is not significant. Lateral flow and tile flow could be also interpreted as “total soil flow”. In SWAT+ check file flow is separated from the lateral flow. Lateral flow proportion is in general higher in regions where terrain slope is higher, one of such areas is western region AII.

Water Balance Ratios

Streamflow/Precipitation	0.39
Baseflow/Total Flow	0.74
Surface Runoff/Total Flow	0.26
Percolation/Precipitation	0.08
Deep Recharge/Precipitation	0.00
ET/Precipitation	0.49

Figure 4: SWAT+ Check screenshot for Jūra. Water balance components and warnings.

2.1.3. Region BIII

Dubysa watershed was used in PAIC (2022) for recalibration in region BIII. Flow was calibrated at the location of station Dubysa_Lyduvenai.

Messages and Warnings

- Surface runoff ratio may be low (< 0.2)
- Groundwater ratio may be low
- Lateral flow is greater than groundwater flow; may indicate a problem
- Surface runoff may be too low
- It is highly recommended that you use at least 1 year of model warmup; 2-5 years is better

Water Balance Ratios

Streamflow/Precipitation	0.27
Baseflow/Total Flow	0.81
Surface Runoff/Total Flow	0.19
Percolation/Precipitation	0.06
Deep Recharge/Precipitation	0.00
ET/Precipitation	0.65

Figure 5: SWAT+ Check screenshot for Dubysa watershed. Water balance components and warnings.

The results of SWAT+ Check for Dubysa watershed are presented in Figure 5 for water quantity. The warnings are similar to those discussed in Regions AI-AII.

2.1.4. Region BIV

Tatula-Trečionys station was used for realibration in the hydrological region BIV. The results of SWAT+ Check for Tatula watershed are presented in Figure 6 for water quantity.

Warnings regarding high lateral flow are the same as in regions AII-BIII.

Water Balance Ratios

Streamflow/Precipitation	0.22
Baseflow/Total Flow	0.63
Surface Runoff/Total Flow	0.37
Percolation/Precipitation	0.07
Deep Recharge/Precipitation	0.00
ET/Precipitation	0.68

Figure 6: SWAT+ Check screenshot for Tatula watershed. Water balance components and warnings.

2.1.5. Region BV

Hydrometric station Nevėžis-Panevėžys was used for recalibration in the central hydrological region BV. The results of SWAT+ Check for upstream Nevėžis watershed are presented in Figure 7 for water quantity.

SWAT+ Check warnings are the same as in PAIC&VUB (2014).

Figure 7: SWAT+ Check screenshot for upstream Nevėžis watershed. Water balance components and warnings.

2.1.6. Region BVI

Hydrometric station Mituva-Žindaičiai was used for the recalibration in the central hydrological region BVI. The results of SWAT+ Check for upstream Mituva watershed are presented in Figure 8 for water quantity.

SWAT+ Check warnings are the same as in PAIC&VUB (2014).

Water Balance Ratios

Streamflow/Precipitation	0.22
Baseflow/Total Flow	0.74
Surface Runoff/Total Flow	0.26
Percolation/Precipitation	0.08
Deep Recharge/Precipitation	0.00
ET/Precipitation	0.68

Figure 8: SWAT+ Check screenshot for Mituva watershed. Water balance components and warnings.

2.1.7. Region BVII

Hydrometric station Nemunėlis-Kvetkai was used for recalibration in the central hydrological region BVII. The results of SWAT+ Check for downstream Nemunėlis watershed are presented in Figure 9 for water quantity.

SWAT+ Check warnings are the same as in PAIC&VUB (2014).

Water Balance Ratios

Streamflow/Precipitation	0.25
Baseflow/Total Flow	0.71
Surface Runoff/Total Flow	0.29
Percolation/Precipitation	0.09
Deep Recharge/Precipitation	0.00
ET/Precipitation	0.68

Figure 9: SWAT+ Check screenshot for downstream Nemunėlis watershed. Water balance components and warnings.

2.1.8. Region CIX

Hydrometric station Verknė-Verbyliškės was used for recalibration in the southeastern hydrological region CIX. The results of SWAT+ Check for Verknė watershed are presented in Figure 10 for water quantity.

SWAT+ Check warnings are the same as in PAIC&VUB (2014) regarding surface flow, while the same as in previously considered regions regarding the lateral flow.

Figure 10: SWAT+ Check screenshot for Verknė watershed. Water balance components and warnings.

2.1.9. Region CX

Station Širvinta-Liukonys was used for recalibration in hydrological region CX. The results of SWAT+ Check for Širvinta watershed are presented in Figure 11 for water quantity. SWAT+ Check warnings are the same as in PAIC&VUB (2014) where they are analysed in detail.

Messages and Warnings

- Surface runoff ratio may be low (< 0.2)
- Groundwater ratio may be low
- Lateral flow is greater than groundwater flow; may indicate a problem
- Surface runoff may be too low
- It is highly recommended that you use at least 1 year of model warmup; 2-5 years is better

Water Balance Ratios

Streamflow/Precipitation	0.27
Baseflow/Total Flow	0.81
Surface Runoff/Total Flow	0.19
Percolation/Precipitation	0.06
Deep Recharge/Precipitation	0.00
ET/Precipitation	0.62

Figure 11: SWAT+ Check screenshot for Širvinta watershed. Water balance components and warnings.

2.1.10. Region CXI

Hydrometric station Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos was used for the recalibration in the southeastern hydrological region CXI.

The results of SWAT+ Check for Ūla-Pelesa watershed are presented in Figure 12 for water quantity.

SWAT+ Check warnings are the same as in PAIC&VUB (2014).

Water Balance Ratios

Streamflow/Precipitation	0.21
Baseflow/Total Flow	0.97
Surface Runoff/Total Flow	0.03
Percolation/Precipitation	0.18
Deep Recharge/Precipitation	0.01

Figure 12: SWAT+ Check screenshot for Ūla-Pelesa watershed. Water balance components and warnings.

2.1.11. Region CXII

Hydrometric station Svyla-Guntauninkai was used for the recalibration in the southeastern hydrological region CXII.

The results of SWAT+ Check for Birveta watershed are presented in Figure 13 for water quantity. SWAT+ Check warnings are the same as in PAIC&VUB (2014). These warnings are characteristic for the hydrological regions (B and C) and do not reflect problems in the model.

Water Balance Ratios

Streamflow/Precipitation	0.25
Baseflow/Total Flow	0.70
Surface Runoff/Total Flow	0.30
Percolation/Precipitation	0.05
Deep Recharge/Precipitation	0.00
ET/Precipitation	0.65

Figure 13: SWAT+ Check screenshot for Birveta watershed. Water balance components and warnings.

2.1.12. Summary of warnings and water balance

The summary of all warnings and their evaluation is given in Table 2. They have small to none effect on the model reliability:

- Warning #1 is because of SWAT+ does not allows correctly implement the so called warm-up period.
- Warning #5 is generated due the relatively high lateral flow. High lateral flow in general is objective for the regions with higher slope, this is the same as in (PAIC, 2014).
- Warnings #2-5 are already analysed in detail in PAIC&VUB (2014).

Table 2: Summary of SWAT+ Check warnings.

#	Warning	Region	Effect	Comment
1	It is recommended to use longer warm up period	All regions	None	no warm-up in SWAT+
2	Surface runoff ratio may be low	All, BIII, BVI, BVII, CIX, CX, CXI, CXII	Small	PAIC&VUB (2014)
3	Surface runoff may be low	BIII, BV, BVI, CIX, CX, CXI	Small	PAIC&VUB (2014)
4	Groundwater ratio may be low	All, BIII, BIV, BV, CX, CXII	Small	PAIC&VUB (2014)
5	Lateral flow is greater than groundwater	All, BIII, BIV, BV, BVI, BVII, CIX, CX, CXII	None	High lateral flow is natural in regions with higher slope

We noticed that water balance is not achieved by SWAT+ in all waterheds. The precipitation always exceeds the sum of evapotranspiration and all “outflowing” water balance components This disbalance may be as low as 3% in region A1, reach worrying 9% in region CX and even unacceptable 18% level in region CXI.

The situation was investigated, and it was found that SWAT+ fails to account for evapotranspiration and other flow components from the wetlands, while precipitation over wetlands is accounted in the water balance. This bug went unnoticed in the calibration effort PAIC (2022) because the share of wetlands in water and nutrients discharge are very small. Thus, with error of SWAT+ code does not influence practical application of the modelling system. Its fixing is beyond the scope of the present project.

2.2. Improving water quantity and quality model results

Evaluating the water quantity modelling results in PAIC(2022) the place for improvement was noted in watersheds Dubysa-Lyduvenai (frequent zero discharges), Verkne-Verbiliškis (low-flow below the observed values), Širvinta-Liukonys (frequent zero discharges), Merkys (modelling results below observations). The formal calibration criteria were met in these stations, however, Client requested an additional study and improvement of water quantity calibration in these four stations in the final stage of the project. Similarly, Client requested for additional study of nitrate concentration results for stations Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus (summer minimums of N-NO₃ not represented in model) and Būka – aukščiau Baluošo (summer N-NO₃ concentrations too low). The analysis and achievements of the calibration effort is presented in the respective Subsections of the Section 2.2.

2.2.1. Region BIII – hydrology

Dubysa watershed was used in PAIC (2022) for recalibration in region BIII. Flow was calibrated at the location of station Dubysa_Lyduvenai. Although the calibration targets were reached for Dubysa_Lyduvenai, the time graph of the observed and modelled discharges (see Figure 14) indicated frequent zero-flow events. The improvement achieved in the final stage of the project is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges for Dubysa_Lyduvenai. PAIC (2022) in upper Figure, present improvement in lower Figure.

2.2.2. Region BIII – water quality

Dubysa watershed was used in PAIC (2022) for recalibration in region BIII. Water quality was calibrated at the location of station Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus. Although the calibration targets were reached for Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus, the time graph of the observed and modeled nitrate concentrations (see upper Figure 15) indicated frequent nearly zero-N-NO₃ observations not reproduced in the model.

Figure 15: Time graphs of the observed (dots) and modelled (green line) concentrations of N-NO₃ (above) and N-org (below) for Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus. SWAT+.

Mineral nitrogen falls to 0 in observations, but the model is unable to replicate this. As we see in the observations all of the nitrogen transforms into organic nitrogen for which the levels are relatively stable throughout the year. In the model the organic nitrogen highly correlates with the mineral nitrogen and the model is unable to replicate the effect observed in this observation station.

The standard solution to resolve such situation would be higher remineralization transformation rate in the rivers and reservoirs but that doesn't seem to help enough here. The calibration result is a compromise to maintain the total nitrogen balance.

Figure 16: Time graphs of the observed (dots) and modelled (green line) concentrations of N-NO3 for Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus. SWAT2012.

It is also visible in the previous modelling system PAIC&VUB(2014) with SWAT 2012 that the SWAT model was unable to model this low-summer N-NO3 situation, see Figure 16.

2.2.3. Region CIX - hydrology

Hydrometric station Verknė-Verbyliškės was used for recalibration in the southeastern hydrological region CIX. Although the calibration targets were reached for Verknė-Verbyliškės, the time graph of the observed and modeled discharges (see Figure 17) indicated several zero-flow events and generally lower discharges during the low-flow events. The improvement achieved in the final stage of the project is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges at Verknė-Verbyliškės. PAIC (2022) in upper Figure, present improvement in lower Figure.

2.2.4. Region CX – hydrology

Station Širvinta-Liukonys was used for recalibration in hydrological region CX. The calibration targets were reached for Širvinta-Liukonys. However, the time graph of the observed and modeled discharges (see Figure 18) indicated several zero-flow events. The improvement achieved in the final stage of the project is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Time plot model output - green, observations – red for Širvinta-Liukonys watershed. PAIC (2022) in upper Figure, present improvement in lower Figure.

2.2.5. Region CXI – hydrology

Hydrometric station Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos was used for the recalibration in the southeastern hydrological region CXI. The calibration targets were reached for Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos.

However, the time graph of the observed and modelled discharges (see Figure 19) indicated systematically lower values of modelled discharges during the low-flow periods. The improvement achieved in the final stage of the project is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges at Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos. PAIC (2022) in upper Figure, present improvement in lower Figure.

2.2.6. Region CXI – water quality

Water quality station Būka – aukščiau Baluošo. was used for the recalibration in the southeastern hydrological region CXI.

Figure 20: Time graphs of the observed (dots) and modelled (green line) concentrations of N-NO₃ for Būka – aukščiau Baluošo. SWAT+ (upper) and SWAT2012 (lower).

We see a situation where the modeled nitrate concentration is highly seasonal, but in the observed situation it is rather stable throughout the year (upper Figure 20). This station seems to be rather dependent on the reservoir upstream and the settling rate of nutrients in it. Unfortunately, changes in the parameters of the reservoir didn't bring the changes anticipated during the calibration and rechecking process.

We can see that in SWAT 2012 (lower Figure 20) the nitrogen base levels were more appropriate while the average concentrations (which is a calibration target) were too high.

Thus, we conclude that improvements are not possible without compromising the nitrogen balance. This may be related to overall handling of reservoir properties in SWAT models.

3. LIBRARY OF SCRIPTS

Two new scripts were added to the script library prepared in PAIC (2022).

3.1. Land use update

The update of the land use during the modelling period is different in SWAT2012 and SWAT+. The former used *.lup files which are no longer supported in SWAT+. Therefore the land use change was implemented via decision tables. We provide the description of the script which allows for automated handling these decision tables.

One update of the land cover is implemented, similar to PAIC&VUB(2014). The implementation uses a functionality of SWAT+ decision tables that allows updating the area fractions of HRUs. Changed fractions are calculated by the script from two CORINE datasets, see also PAIC&VUB (2014). The script automatically determines the updated HRU fractions according to the following method:

1. The land use classes are aggregated in 7 groups as “Agricultural”, “Pastures”, “Forest”, “Urban”, “Wetlands”, “Water” and “Barren”.
2. For each of the catchments the relative fractions of each of the group of the land use classes are calculated for CORINE 2000 and CORINE 2006.
3. The table containing catchment ID, and 7 numbers – the changes (in %) of the relative fraction of each of the group of land use classes is prepared

The prepared data is further used by the automated system of the generation of the water quality modeling system for creation of decision table that allows the update. Landuse update (LUP) related variables in *settings.py* are under the class *LanduseUpdate*:

1. Variable *update_fractions* contains a scheme and table name of the Postgre table where landuse update proportional fractions per cathment are prepared and stored. Default value of this variable is ("*lup*", "*lupupdate*"). This table contains the following fields:
 - a. *catchmentID* (integer) – catchment ID of subbasin as defined in *CatchmentFile*.
 - b. *Agricultural, Barren, Forest, Pasture, Urban, Water, Wetland* (double) – these fields provide values of update fractions per each landuse group.
2. Variable *lup_date* is a start date of landscape update (*yyyy,mm,dd*), if it is empty () then the landscape update is not applied. Default value of this variable is ().
3. Variables for preparation of the landuse update fractions:
 - a. Variables *classes_1* and *classes_2* define the schema and table names of the two polygon feature classes in Postgre database which define two sequential landuses. Default values of these variables are ("*lup*", "*clc00_lt*") and ("*lup*", "*clc06_lt*").
 - b. Variable *lookup_table* contains the schema and name of Postgre table that defines the relations between the landscape update polygons and the general landuse groups Default value of this variable is ("*lup*", "*luplookup*").

- c. Variables *lu_1_field*, *lu_2_field*, *lookupfield* define the field name of landuse code in, respectively, first landuse table, second landuse table and lookup table. Variable *groupfield* define the field name of landuse group code in the lookup table.
- d. Variables *catchments_1* and *catchments_2* contain Postgre schemas and table names of the polygon classes which will contain the intersection of the *classes_1* and *classes_2* with the subbasin polygons. Default values of these variables are ("*lup*", "*corine2000*") and ("*lup*", "*corine2006*").
- e. Variables *table_1* and *table_2* are Postgre schema and table names of tables where amounts of landuse groups per subbasin will be stored. Default values are ("*lup*", "*lup_table1*") and ("*lup*", "*lup_table2*").

3.2. Managed drainage

Introduction of managed drainage into fields was realized within new current SWAT version capabilities – the decision tables.

This HRU level measure allows changing of tile drainage depth by means of user supplied decision table. Filtering by landuse code and soil type are allowed. Application fraction is controlled by parameter *application_fraction*.

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(
    measures.measure_managed_drainage,
    watershednamelist=watershednamelist,
    application_fraction=1.0,
    landuse_list=[],
    soillist=[],
    fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,
    tiledraindecisiontable=drain_control_dtl,
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

Tiledraindecisiontable is a string containing decision table in SWAT+ format. For a description of format of decision table see SWAT+ input output manual².

The sample decision table that allows introducing of managed drainage is given in the variable *measureFunctions.ManagedDrainageDecisionTable.drain_control_dtl*, see also Table 3. It allows for opening of tile drains by settings the depth of drains to 1100 mm in spring (day of year 65) and closing of them in autumn (by settings depth of drains to 0 mm) (day of year 295).

- The first line of decision table is a comment line.
- The second line contains, sequentially, the name of decision table, the number of conditions, the number of alternatives and the number of actions.

² <https://swatplus.gitbook.io/docs/user/io>

- Next, the lines describing the conditions follow (comment line and 2 condition lines in the example case). Conditions in the example file are for the day of the year (variable name *jday*). For the list of possible conditions consult the SWAT+ input output manual.
- Further, the lines describing the actions follow (comment line and 2 action lines in the example case). Actions in the example file are of type *drain_control*. This action type allows setting of depth of drain tiles that need to be provided in column named *const*.

Table 3: Sample decision table.

name	conds	alts	acts	!open drains in spring and close in autumn					
control_drainage	2		2	2					
var	obj	obj_n	lim_var	lim_op	lim_cnst	alt1	alt2		
jday	hru	0	null	-	65.00	=	-	!open drains on day 65	
jday	hru	0	null	-	295.00	-	=	!close drains on day 295	
act_typ		obj	obj_n	name	option	const	const2	fp	outcome
drain_control		hru	0	open_spring	null	1100.0	1.000	null	y n
drain_control		hru	0	close_fall	null	0.0000	1.000	null	n y

4. MODELLING OF WATER QUALITY IMPROVEMENT MEASURES

The study was performed to assess the reliability of the modelling system for the modelling of water quality improvement measures. The use of the scripts implementing various measures is tested in the further sections of this Chapter. If not stated otherwise the study is concentrated on a sample catchment LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019. Each of the further Sections elaborates on the observations of the Agency then testing the implementing of various measures in this catchment.

4.1. Fertilization timing

Observation: It is not clear what is behind adaptive fertilization timing measures and how this timing could be controlled in the measure script (only application fraction, landuse and soils can be controlled, but not timing). And for which soils/landuse types it is applied (only agricultural land or all territory?). In fact, the measures with default parameters increase pollution by up to 18 % in winter – strange outcome from environmental measure.

The fertilization timing measure requires modification of the management practice defined in the plant passports (according to definition in PAIC (2015)³) for involved plants. The management practice table is located in table *plantmng_fertilizertiming* under schema *measures*.

As a default we have put a dummy management practice table one that is the same as for the case without measures. It means that by default this measure should give no effect.

Table 4: Default table of management praxis for winter wheat.

id	swat_id	opnprk	optype	hu	value	value2	value_s	day	mon
283	WWHT	1.5	Nitr	0.0493675	0.5				
284	WWHT	2.5	Nitr	0.2388165	0.25				
285	WWHT	3.5	Nitr	0.3505621	0.25				
286	WWHT	4.5	H	1.1					
287	WWHT	5.5	T	0.0057526	1				
288	WWHT	6.5	T	0.0791582	2				
289	WWHT	7.5	T	0.1476506	4				
290	WWHT	8.5	Phos	0.1476506	1				
291	WWHT	9.5	Manure	0.1476506	1				
292	WWHT	10.5	P	0.1541307	1115.2105				

If the effect of measure is needed then the plant management table should be modified accordingly. Following two tables show the default (Table 4) and the modified (Table 5) plant management praxis for winter wheat. Modified praxis distributes the application of the mineral nitrogen fertilizer more evenly in time (changes marked in green). There is some effect of this small change as could be seen in Figure 21.

³ Definition of management practice: Annex 1. Management practice for crops in SWAT model
Definitions of measures: Chapter 5. AGRICULTURAL OPTIMISATION MEASURES

Table 5: Modified table of management praxis for winter wheat.

id	swat_id	opnprk	optype	hu	value	value2	value_s	day	mon
283	WWHT	1.5	Nitr	0.0493675	0.4				
284	WWHT	2.5	Nitr	0.2388165	0.35				
285	WWHT	3.5	Nitr	0.3505621	0.25				
286	WWHT	4.5	H	1.1					
287	WWHT	5.5	T	0.0057526	1				
288	WWHT	6.5	T	0.0791582	2				
289	WWHT	7.5	T	0.1476506	4				
290	WWHT	8.5	Phos	0.1476506	1				
291	WWHT	9.5	Manure	0.1476506	1				
292	WWHT	10.5	P	0.1541307	1115.2105				

Figure 21: Effect of fertilization timing measure in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

4.2. Advanced fertilization techniques

Observation: Advanced fertilization measures with default parameters and inject technology in LielupeMI/Svete does not produce any difference from the base. This measure might be incorrectly implemented.

Inject is the default setting in calibrated model– so no changes are expected using the default parameters. Selecting any other application type according to the documentation of measure script library in PAIC (2022) will produce notable changes. Figure 22 demonstrates results for the measure with *drill* application type.

Figure 22: Effect of advanced fertilization (*drill*) measure in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

4.3. Fertilization reduction measure

Observation: Fertilization reduction measure seems to have relatively small effect even if 50 % reduction in N fertilizer is set in the LielupeMI/Svete watershed. This measure might be have implementation flaws (needs checking); Up to 11 % reduction, but only in winter – because surpluses are only leached out in winter?

Figure 23: Effect of 50% fertilization reduction in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

Similar measure was implemented also in PAIC (2015) based on SWAT2012. We compared the modelled nitrate load in LielupeMI/Svete watershed with 50% fertilizer reduction from previous project with the results given by this measure in SWAT+. The reduction of NO₃ load in both cases are similar (see Figures 23 and 24). There are no implementation flaws for this measure in the measure script library.

Figure 24: Effect of 50% fertilization reduction measure in SWAT2012 on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 1997-2012.

4.4. Filter strips and grassed waterways measure

Observation: It is not clear how to change filter strip parameters in filter strip measure (technical question for non-python user), the same with grass waterways measure. Does it apply only to HRUs where river beds are present? Share of filter strip in HRU is difficult to understand what it would mean in terms of buffer width. Channel length parameter in grassed waterways is also difficult to comprehend – what does default value of 0.75 km means – for each stream only 0.75 km measure applies or what? In addition, filter strip and grass waterways measures with default parameters produced no effects at all (grass waterways) or effects are negligible (filter strips). Why is it so not clear.

The filter strip measure is a HRU level measure, see PAIC (2022). The filter strip parameters are applied to all HRUs that fall under selection criteria. User supplies these criteria in a call to `scenarios.implementMeasure` function. In the measure implementation we use the same parameters that SWAT+ uses to describe filter strips. See the effect of application of the filter strip measure in Figure 25.

The same explanation applies also to grassed waterways measure. For the description of meanings of parameters, we refer to SWAT+ I/O manual.

Figure 25: Effect of measure *filterstrips* in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

Figure 26: Effect of measure *grassedwaterways* on N-NO3 load in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

When testing the grassed waterways measure, we also checked the SWAT+ source code for the implementation of grassed waterways and found multiple bugs there. The main error ensures that the grassed waterways are effectively switched off even if user requests them. We modified the SWAT+ source code to allow grassed waterways to be enabled. From the SWAT+ source code it is also obvious that grassed waterways do not have direct influence on the nitrate loads (see Figure 26), but only to phosphates and organic nitrogen (Figure 27) and phosphorus.

Figure 27: Effect of measure *grassedwaterways* on organic nitrogen load in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

4.5. Land use change

Observation: Land use conversion in LielupeMi/Svete watershed with default parametres and conversion from winter wheat to winter pasture resulted in N load increase (up to 17 % in winter). The increase was even more significant (up to 157 % in winter) for landuse group conversion measure with default parametres (same basin) when converting from agricultural land to forest land. This measure might be incorrectly implemented.

Figure 28: Effect of conversion of agricultural land to forest. SWAT+ for LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

Similar measures were implemented in previous project PAIC (2015). We compared the effect of measures in SWAT2012 and SWAT+ (see Figures 28 and 29). Both give increase of nitrate load when agricultural land uses are substituted by forest. Thus, the responses are similar, and these measure is implemented correctly.

Figure 29: Effect of conversion of agricultural land to forest. SWAT2012 for LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 1997-2012.

Figure 30: Effect of converting arable lands to forest combined with closure of tile drainage in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

The lower nitrate loads from the forest land in the model comes mainly from the absence of tile drains in the forest. In the measure script library it is possible to combine landuse change measure with the measure that closes the tile drains

(*measure_tiledrain*), by setting the depths of drains (parameter *dp*) to 0. To invoke such scenario user should at first call the landuse change measure and sequentially request the closure of tile drains on landuse code *FRST*. Effect of such combined measure in reducing nitrate load is shown in Figure 30.

Figure 31: Effect of transforming arable lands to grasslands in SWAT+ for LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

Figure 32: Effect of transforming arable lands to grasslands in SWAT2012 for LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 1998-2000.

Results of comparison of changing of arable lands to grasslands between SWAT2012 and SWAT+ models are shown in figures 31-33. Effects are somewhat different. We

found that SWAT produces temporal variation in response to the measure (compare Figures 31-32 for different 3 year periods), owing to the fact that grasslands are perennial. It means that estimating the effect for a short time period of 3 years are not advisable for this measure, and longer time slices should be used, compare Figures 32-33 for shorter and longer time slices.

We also note that changing the arable land to grasslands is achieved by converting agricultural landuse codes to winter pasture *WPAS*. The management praxis for this type of landuse contains also fertilization. If the measure is aimed at converting to the unmanaged perennial grasslands, it is advised to combine this measure with reduction of fertilization by 100%.

Figure 33: Effect of transforming arable lands to grasslands in SWAT2012 for LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 1997-2012.

4.6. Sediment ponds and wetlands

Observation: It is not clear what is the meaning of parameters in the land conversion to sedimentation ponds and wetlands measure, what could be their value range etc. The results for LielupeMI/Svete basin with default parameters seems very good in terms of pollution reduction effectiveness, thus understanding the parameters and how to manage them is especially important.

Sedimentation ponds and wetlands are implemented by surface storage of SWAT+ (*wetlands.wet*). It is supposed to allow part of each of HRUs to be converted to pond or wetland with given properties. Further, it is supposed that loads from HRUs will pass through this pond or wetland to reduce the loads.

We analyzed the source code of SWAT+ and found that this is incorrectly implemented in SWAT+. Present SWAT+ source code assumes that entire HRU is wet and don't use fractional inputs. In addition to that there are obvious errors in SWAT+ source code

related to sediment ponds and wetlands. The fixing of these errors are beyond the scope of present project, therefore we do not recommend to use this measure for now.

4.7. Managed drainage

Observation: It is not clear how the parameters in managed drainage measure should be managed in order to achieve managed drainage effects of let's say artificially increasing or/and decreasing of water table (level). Besides, the measure with default parameters seems not to be working – even slight increases in NO₃-N pollution in LielupeMI/Svete basin is observed. Therefore, this measure might be incorrectly implemented.

The managed drainage measure allows changing of tile drainage depth by means of user supplied decision table. It up to the user to provide this table. The example supplied with the modelling system allows for opening of tile drains by settings the depth of drains to 1100 mm in spring (day of year 65) and closing of them in autumn by setting the depth of drains to 0 mm (day of year 295). Figure 34 shows the effect of the measure.

Figure 34: Effect of managed drainage measure in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

4.8. Catch crops

Observation: running catch crop measure for LielupeMI/Svete watershed with default parameters the effect is very tiny, almost unnoticeable. Needs checking if working correctly.

The catch crop measure requires modification of the management practice which is provided in plant passports – according to definition in PAIC (2015) for involved plants. The management practice is defined in table *plantmng_catchcrops* under schema *measures*.

We checked that SWAT+ handling of management praxis involving two plants (in this case main crop and catch crop) is different from SWAT2012. There was also a bug in SWAT+ source code that incorrectly determined the plant code of a scheduled operation if there is more than one plant involved.

Figure 35: Effect of catch crop measure in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

Figure 36: Effect of catch crop measure in SWAT2012 on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 1997-2012.

We corrected the SWAT+ code. We also modified the script to allow for multiple plants in management praxis. We checked the results of the measure both in the present system SWAT+, and in the SWAT2012 modelling system of PAIC (2015), see Figures 35 and 36 The magnitude of effect is similar.

4.9. Planting of winter crops

Observation. Planting of winter crops measure (default parameters, the same watershed) resulted in up to 56 % increase in loads in winter – is it because of used fertilizer and possibly little covering of land from leaching?

Figure 37: Effect of planting winter crops in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

The measure of planting winter crops requires modification of the management practice in plant passports according to definition in PAIC (2015) for involved plants. The management practice table is located in table *plantmng_plantingofwintercrops* under schema *measures*.

We checked that SWAT+ handling of management praxis involving two plants (in this case main crop and winter crop) is different from SWAT2012. There was also a bug in SWAT+ source code that incorrectly determined the plant code of scheduled operation if there was more than one plant involved. We corrected the SWAT+ code. We also modified our script to allow for multiple plants in management praxis. We checked the results of the measure both in the present system and in the modelling system of PAIC (2015), Figures 37 and 38. The magnitude of effect is similar.

Figure 38: Effect of planting winter crops in SWAT2012 on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 1997-2012.

4.10. Plant cover in winter

Observation. Winter cover through winter measures (default parameters, the same watershed) produced negligible effects – is measure implemented well in the system?

Figure 39: Effect of plant cover in winter in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

The measure of plant cover in winter requires a modification of the management practice in plant passports – according to definition in PAIC (2015) for involved plants.

The management practice table is located in table *plantmng_plantcoverinwinter* under schema *measures*.

We checked that SWAT+ handling of management praxis involving two plants (in this case the main crop and catch crop) is different from SWAT2012. There was also a bug in SWAT+ source code that incorrectly determined the plant code of scheduled operation if there is more than one plant involved. We corrected the SWAT+ code. We also modified our script to allow for multiple plants in management praxis. We checked the results of the measure both in the present system and in the modelling system of PAIC (2015), see Figures 39 and 40. The magnitude of effect is similar.

Figure 40: Effect of plant cover in winter in SWAT2012 on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 1997-2012.

4.11. No-plough measure

Observation. With no plough measures (the same watershed with default parameters) negligible effects are spotted. That is strange.

The no-plough measure corresponds to agricultural optimisation measure “No-plough technology” in PAIC (2015). Its realisation relies on the management practice and parameters (*plant passports*) table for the measure, derived in PAIC (2015) with the help of agricultural expert. The plant passports for the measure are located in table *plantmng_noploughtechnology* of scheme *measures* in the PostgreSQL database of the project. The plant passports are the same as in PAIC (2015).

We checked the results of the measure both in the present system and in the modelling system of PAIC (2015), Figures 41-42. Results are similar. It means that there are no implementation errors. In case the users need to modify the plant passports according to their needs, they can provide their own table of plant passports and place it under table *plantmng_noploughtechnology* of scheme *measures*.

Figure 41: Effect of no-plough measure in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

Figure 42: Effect of no-plough measure in SWAT2012 on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 1997-2012.

4.12. Substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing

Observation. With autumn to spring plough measure (same watershed, default parameters) no effect is felt at all after application of this measure. Is the measure well configured?

The measure of substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing corresponds to the agricultural optimisation measure “Substituting autumn ploughing with spring

ploughing” in PAIC (2015). Its realisation relies on the management practice and parameters (*plant passports*) table for the measure, developed in PAIC(2015) with the help of agricultural expert. The plant passports for the measure are located in table *plantmng_substitutingautumnploughingwithspringploughing* of scheme *measures* in the PostgreSQL database of the project. The plant passports are the same as in (PAIC, 2015).

Figure 43: Effect of substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

Figure 44: Effect of substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing in SWAT2012 on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 1997-2012.

We checked the results of the measure both in the present system and in the modelling system of PAIC, (2015), Figures 43, 44. Results are similar. It means that there are no implementation errors. In case when users need to modify the plant passports according to their needs, they can provide their own table of plant passports and place it under table *plantmng_substitutingautumnploughingwithspringploughing* of schema *measures*.

4.13. Postponing a sod ploughing to late autumn

Observation. With postponing sod ploughing to late autumn measure (same watershed, default parameters) no effect is felt at all after application of this measure. Is the measure well configured?

Figure 45: Effect of postponing a sod ploughing to late autumn in SWAT+ on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 2017-2019.

The measure corresponds to the agricultural optimisation measure “*Postponing a sod ploughing to late autumn*” in PAIC (2015). Its realisation relies on the management practice and parameters (*plant passports*) table for the measure, derived in PAIC (2015) with the help of agricultural expert. The plant passports for the measure are located in the table *plantmng_postponingasodploughingtolateautumn* of schema *measures* in the PostgreSQL database of the project. The plant passports are the same as in PAIC (2015).

We checked the results of the measure both in the present system and in the modelling system of PAIC (2015), Figures 45, 46. Results are similar. It means that there are no implementation errors. In case, when users need to modify the plant passports according to their needs, they can provide their own table of plant passports and place it under table *plantmng_postponingasodploughingtolateautumn* of schema *measures*.

Figure 46: Effect of postponing a sod ploughing to late autumn in SWAT2012 on LielupeMI/Svete catchment, years 1997-2012.

5. SWAT+ SOURCE CODE CHANGES

The correction of the SWAT+ source code errors as the list of changes made by Consultant in the reference SWAT+ source code were included in Section 2.3.1 of PAIC(2022) and presented in github repository⁴. Several (6) further bugs were identified and corrected in the final stage of the project (boldified in the list below), therefore we herewith renew the list for the complete reference of hanges made during the project:

1. Wrong output parameter unit. File *ru_day.txt*
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/4d8678d81f01cd79a1a7c74fb90c691ae9aa8b8d#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
2. Wrong output parameter unit. File *channel_sd_day.txt*
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/cdf7c476bc205e16098fde4f558aa3983192a5f3#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
3. Output variables increase all the time (time step). File *soil_nutcarb_out.txt*
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/c6c259351c2577d5bdbfee3fa5bc98b0f491ef57#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
4. Incorectly calculated channel depth. That leads to very small channel outflow. File *ch_watqual4.f90* (*rchdep = 0.*)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/764564e06fb0d8786a42789cdbc5b5d9fe7fddcc#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
5. Variables are misnamed (exchanged *surq_gen* <=> *surq_cont*)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/7a9c54eed89cbbfd5f8667ac8916ac4877320060#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
6. Surfaces runoff processes are not running in regular case. Mismatched (exchanged) wetland and regular cases.
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/d8a575c61e33339f1dd82c1e379880ac08c80ec9#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
7. Coefficients **cn3_swf** and **perco** are initialised to constant values if the tile drain is on
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/d588df775f37fa55a06da175d5b30d32ee0b07eb#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>

⁴ https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commits/main/source_codes

8. Evapotranspiration model differs from SWAT (coefficient **esco**) comparing SWAT theoretical documentation TWRI(2011)⁵ Eq 2:2.3.17 with the source code rev.627/etact.f
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/e652f28d1665f32b06b63d664c681d4bf8af4fb3#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
9. Evapotranspiration model differs from SWAT. According to TWRI(2011) Eq 2:2.3.18 & source code rev.627/etact.f
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/f5401037f379defa733ee107d249287d37e6d19c#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
10. Aquifer nitrogen flow units and initial content are incorrect
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/21af44f544e4af0d2aca112228dff29d91dfd7#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
11. The computation of the travel time of the lateral flow is switched on
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/cf5e71eb7a838335e35b01e74ff4e57771a5e18d#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
12. The computation of the lateral subsurface flow from first soil layer is switched on
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/d2563c25ab187bbf7be677bec3db435807d6e47a#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
13. Redundant line with wrong code is removed
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/cd931978ea8544d064d399069a8886cc7e407440#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
14. *dep_imp* variable is introduced (like in SWAT v.627).
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/a494ec84e131c3c85d16a3213bf1aef893904e34#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
15. A possibility to control output of files *wetland_*.txt* separately from the *reservoir_*.txt* is introduced:
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/dff27eed54cdbcfd82bac88884c7f287df7c8c054#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
16. Module *wetland_control.f90* containing uninitialized variables is bypassed
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/2a60358aceb00005a0a046c>

⁵ <https://swat.tamu.edu/media/99192/swat2009-theory.pdf>

[0a4961c7538539485#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372](https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/0a4961c7538539485#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372)

17. Delay time for aquifers is introduced (like in SWAT v.627)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/de55a5e7d4e1e92aac5196ec3fced92eeee6ee0#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
18. Evaporation module is changed (like in SWAT v.627)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/3b1e2bff30186326fbad9f98c7c156317f5b10ec#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
19. Error in search procedure. Uninitialized variable "aqu_found"
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/a64dd6aeca7c620caeac491b6499d1655ddab248>
20. Corrected snow pack temperature
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/6e248856a34351c3450bcee6bfc38b63f67beadf>
21. Corrected output_losses_header1
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/062b171a219a900fc538abefe07933097e0c15fa>
22. Half-life of NO3 implemented
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/8bea0a7c778f50df9824567e3126cbad79f77893>
23. Update fresh residue plants and soil layers procedure
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/88c0b3b45718724fd75a92f45758715cd8b12ff9>
24. Fresh residue tillage mixing added
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/028e92666381df3e130dc4454b95aed7c95e4c04>
25. Mgt_kill operation: add above ground mass to soil fresh residue pool
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/8b8756b00ef574b38d25491643a81cb14fdcce1f>
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/b177c68d0b0f7f88dc84cbf9f08bb12cb4a9193e>
26. Fresh organic nutrients remineralization added
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/7cdf7b30a0a1dfcae45b9881db9768e11db91b7b>
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/831cfd17466b27b95510ac2f60aaca42ed8049a3>

27. Bugfix for tillage of fresh organic residue mixing
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/6d89f0b887f043c8638a765009feb363c6e6e8d5>
28. Corrected soil nitrate denitrification formula
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/d367c61606555e4cfcf4093410caef757b6c3514>
29. Organic fertilizer added to fresh organic pool (as in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/6db7844c520e7c8036d7ead14fef4ead57fc0823>
30. Harvest index routines modified to correspond to SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/f873c980f69592fd8b0e44ca74384c15d2fad922>
31. Corrected sediment yield calculations
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/64060bd9ea1ae88d04ca839b77918300514261e5>
32. Distribution of plant nitrogen uptake like in SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/324111ac9ca82dac768ae193bc644b85495148fd>
33. Leaf area index growth dependent on total stress like in SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/d1d4d26ec4b1ef4746589d5334cadaac599088f4>
34. Possibility to input initial organic phosphorus and nitrogen in soil layer implemented (as in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/85bfa1e220cff7a72f7013849f862a08801b2632>
35. Changed routine for the biomass growth (bioday)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/b46ea5b770bdd8a764222a3ccbc3756048d365da>
36. Implemented soil carbon initialization from file
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/9697215d7508345b67086a18f9e3ffef4db87885>
37. Restored possibility to select soil phosphorus model as in SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/62d51dcec2b3fc2ab7a2d6e72bfba466a324e7ab>
38. Fixed units of conversion factor in soil initialization routine
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/c737f7f73be45517ead1e0d28b5e1a28e403fa9b>

39. Implemented soil organic phosphorus initialization
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/df657d3117125b6d448b6d1175994514a1e1ddc>
40. Implemented phosphorus in surface runoff from residue (as in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/566d7567fbff3a2ec9153c9af9ef756833a3c9c>
41. Implemented initialization of soil mineral phosphorus un nitrogen from input file (as in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/9aa67e5e64418c19406620b306cfb72da8b260e7>
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/7f26f6e9dda43bc5a71f00a497f2ec2ddce99cac>
42. Formula for initial stable soil phosphorus pool should use carbon concentration not mass per area
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/f78905f02d36c9a33b999268b5ea5d53441dfca6>
43. Code merged with swat official version 13apr2022-Version-60_5_4
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/f9cfe948775a3871dd9fa983f726e0fc2155f193>
44. Simulation.out header fixed
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/2b9f3b90b40b1071f1f958e9a7e9384edfa6941b>
45. PSP calculation should contain carbon concentration not mass per area
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/733b0a2d1ee1b3f896eec74a57cfb6bc47c3fb7>
46. Fix for concentration based mixing in tillage
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/e44dba159f2ddf06ac4cc010f1223815a51dbeb5>
47. Coefficient nperco_lchtile enabled
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/9764d1842217c09a356772fb682cee966ece3a3d>
48. Revert soil soluble phosphorus routines to previous SWAT+ version to correspond to SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/8b8ff55f980a5d4a400140485af3976aa1362d06>
49. Bugfix in phosphorus sediment calculations
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/dbb3cae2fa72168cadd0484c8950545adbbf5a6a>

50. Change LAI, add leaf mass to residue at dormancy for perennials
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/4ca991f5dfc015956c6430034b014eb7d48439fa>
51. Implemented leaf senescence dependent on plant accumulated phu
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/5f6a9fd085b46f18be99ad096384b34678636501>
52. Leaf drop should affect total plant mass – fixed
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/765d01eefb290e78a0b94446688517ae3a5e660e>
53. Dormancy for forests implemented
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/96e5dfc9801168ac95bb636b54959da55cbd178c>
54. Plant partitioning for forests, additional parameter included
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/dc4874937d95365ea11d9d606feeb97f4662135e>
55. End of year management operations added (as in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/27ec883b0edbdd338688dd54822734b7d907fce9>
56. Bugfix - no need to reset phuacc after harvest only operation
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/c73dfce5eeb51ac9ecd64f711c3bb7e7eee4eb7b>
57. Nutrients outflowing from reservoir was not subtracted from reservoir - fixed
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/7ea920867cd7ea185434dc97ec22aa9de074896a>
58. Implemented reservoir settling rate as in SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/448473165355da58056918f2ac84ddb01aac2cbd>
59. Reservoir initialization bug fix
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/5f0d0c9f02cb3f8c73f094072618395a2bed32f3>
60. Minimal flow from reservoir implemented
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/730267719a4c2d464ea5c98e269dda3530b352f9>
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/25d93a1eba9754bbd09c10b1b820945dc4f99514>
61. Repaired aquifer flow numerical scheme that was unstable (implemented order of operations as was in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/dfde88519d5ede6951e3e01e90df43509d48a759>

62. Corrected uninitialized output variable in action "hru_fr_update"
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/9b75dd914539b7d061946399e25cf8acce87c02>
63. Aquifer nutrient output dimension changed to kg/ha
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/bec9744e2e3639b3a17323f5711443e0c30fcee5>
64. Corrected routing unit output
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/1a248048fd12b4ec0c298cd99509406ea0413ea8>
65. Routing unit number added to routing unit output
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/339081f285aa0f7148cbd6019b2467ce2a482a3f>
66. Enabled and bugfix source code for grassed waterways
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/3fc00b39edc86951e374f07a24fa02ab50cdbaa1>
67. Bugfix in plant determination at scheduled management operation
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/db46d5a3ec55775db9221dbab37fac9c6dd8f0a0>

6. MISCELLANEOUS

The acceptance of the 1st Interim report PAIC (2021) was conditional. Let us consider the addressing of these conditions.

1. Distributed version control system for the Project should be shared with Agency

The distributed version control system was established in May-2021 and described in PAIC (2022), Section 4.1

2. GIS data handling `lu.py` and `gdr_impervious.py` scripts should be rewritten to open source libraries.

The mentioned scripts were rewritten as one script `lu.py` avoiding use of ArcGIS libraries; they are implemented in the modelling system during the last stage of the project.

The script `lu.py` is aimed for the preparation of unified landuse layer from different data sources. It performs the data combination as described in the first intermediate report PAIC (2021), section 3.2.2. Script input data are declared crops, forest cadaster, abandoned lands, GDR geospatial data and imperviousness data. The output is unified landuse layer. The geospatial union operation between four of the datasets (except imperviousness) should be performed by user.

3. Visualization and analysis tools should be prepared for the reviewing modeling results and comparing it to monitoring data.

PAICSWAT and dedicated scripts for SWAT+ were developed during the 2nd stage of the project and described in PAIC (2022), Section 4.2.

4. Ensure that all water bodies are fully covered in the renewed system (codes for the missing water bodies: 100102581, 100102201, 300103801).

The water bodies in question were included in the modelling system in May-2021.

5. Ensure that land use change are included in the system through decision tables.

The modelling system was upgraded with the land use change through decision tables in the last stage of the project and described in Section 3.1 of this report.

7. TRAINING AND DESCRIPTION OF ACTIONS

7.1. Training

The training for the Agency personnel were performed as 3 hands-on MS Teams session on 8th, 16th and 19th of September, 2022.

The training included acquiring the necessary skills for the use of the modelling system in the following four topics:

1. Current system and results

The first topic covered

- Quick overview of building blocks of the system
- Acquiring results in current state of the system (running script, getting results)
- Analysing results (PAICSWAT, GIS, other)

2. Understanding the script system

The second topic covered the following skills

- Learning what scripts are there
- Editing of variables and changing input parameters
- Making changes through scripts
- Implementing the changes and calculation of modified system

3. Management of input data

The third topic addressed the management of input data

- Learning what input data there is and at what level is it editable
- Standard procedures of input data change
- Implementing input data change in the system and calculation of modified system

4. Additional scripts and possibilities

The fourth topic was dealing with the advanced skills

- Calculating a part of the system
- Implementing fine resolution setups for selected watersheds
- Getting from raw data to input data

7.2. Description of actions

The structure of the modelling system is provided in Chapter 4.1 of PAIC (2022) and Annex “Electronic deliverables” of PAIC (2021). In this Section we include description of the workflow for upgrading model data (Subsection 7.2.1) and running scripts for implementation of water quality improvement measures (Subsection 7.2.2).

7.2.1. Data update

Data update is required on the arrival of new data. Let us consider the thematic data blocks which may be updated periodically.

1. Meteorological data.

Script reads the data from the folder `Setup_2020_common\Data\Observations\`. The relevant files are `Weatherdata_preprocessed.txt` and `*.sta` (defined in `settings.py`). The workflow is shown in Figure 47, while the screenshots of relevant files in Figures 48-49.

Figure 47: Workflow for updating meteorological data.

```

→→→T→Tmin→Tmax→Prec→W10→RHUM→SolarCRLE
→→→degC→degC→degC→mm/day→m/s→%→MJ/m2/dayCRLE
Station→Date→→→→→→→→→CRLE
1→1994.01.01→1.3→0.5→1.6→4.6→2.4→95.0→→→CRLE
1→1994.01.02→0.4→-0.2→→0.8→1.3→2.4→95.0→→→CRLE
1→1994.01.03→-0.8→→-3.0→→-0.2→→0.0→1.9→97.0→→→CRLE
1→1994.01.04→-3.0→→-5.3→→-1.5→→0.2→4.0→92.0→→→CRLE
1→1994.01.05→-0.5→→-1.3→→0.3→2.3→2.3→96.0→→→CRLE
1→1994.01.06→0.3→-0.3→→1.4→2.5→2.5→98.0→→→CRLE
1→1994.01.07→0.8→0.1→1.1→0.8→3.4→97.0→→→CRLE
1→1994.01.08→0.6→0.7→→1.6→0.0→3.5→94.0→→→CRLE

```

Figure 48: File `Weatherdata_preprocessed.txt`.

```

ID→Name→→Lon→LatCRLE
1→BIRŽAI→547577→6229850CRLE
2→DOTNUVA→491554→6140541CRLE
3→DŪKŠTAS→645246→6155923CRLE
4→KAUNAS→489306→6083039CRLE
5→KYBARTAI→→421450→6055882CRLE
6→KLAIPĖDA→→315789→6181535CRLE
7→LAUKUVA→388713→6166066CRLE
8→LAZDIJAI→→468489→6010793CRLE
9→MTDA→→310659→6135312CRLE

```

Figure 49: File `Weatherdata_preprocessed.sta`.

2. Hydrological and water quality data.

Script reads the data from the folder `Setup_2020_common\Data\Observations\`. The relevant files are `Qobs.txt`, `WQobs.txt` and `*.sta` (defined in `settings.py`). The workflow is shown in Figure 50, while the screenshots of relevant `Qobs.txt` and `Qobs.sta` files in Figures 51-52.

Figure 50: Workflow for updating hydrological and water quality data.

```

1  STAT → DATE → QCRLE
2  → m3/sCRLE
3  2 → 1993.01.01 → 1.149999976CRLE
4  2 → 1993.01.02 → 1.100000024CRLE
5  2 → 1993.01.03 → 0.899999976CRLE
6  2 → 1993.01.04 → 0.850000024CRLE
7  2 → 1993.01.05 → 0.800000012CRLE
8  2 → 1993.01.06 → 0.899999976CRLE
9  2 → 1993.01.07 → 1.049999952CRLE
10 2 → 1993.01.08 → 1.100000024CRLE
11 2 → 1993.01.09 → 1.909999967CRLE
12 2 → 1993.01.10 → 3.420000076CRLE

```

Figure 51: File *Qobs.txt*.

```

ID → Name → X → Y → AreaCRLE
2 → Akmena-Danė-Kretinga → 326235 → 6195741 → 292CRLE
3 → Akmena-Paakmenis → 392183 → 6151940 → 314CRLE
4 → Aunuva-Aunuvėnai → 422769 → 6191311 → 93.8CRLE
5 → Bartuva-Skuodas → 345835 → 6241204 → 612CRLE
59 → Daugyvenė-Rimšoniai → 497633 → 6210175 → 494CRLE
6 → Dubysa-Lyduvėnai → 442477 → 6152658 → 1070CRLE
68 → Istras-Talackoniai → 522342 → 6209069 → 110CRLE
73 → Jūra-Pajūris → 374811 → 6147316 → 876CRLE
8 → Jūra-Tauragė → 390616 → 6125334 → 1690CRLE
9 → Klaipėdos kanalas-Lankupiai → 333276 → 6152639 → CRLE
10 → Kražantė-Pluskiai → 426554 → 6159872 → 371CRLE
69 → Kulpe-Siauliai → 458476 → 6206084 → CRLE
12 → Lėvuo-Bernatoniai → 517872 → 6184111 → 1130CRLE

```

Figure 52: File *Qobs.sta*.

3. Point source data

The point sources may be added either by the dedicated script described in Section 3.1.3 of PAIC (2022) or directly updating the files in the folder *Setup_2020_common\Data\PointSources*.

The workflow is shown in Figure 53; note that it slightly differs for monthly and annual point source data. To modify point source data by dedicated script user shall

- Provide additional point source files in *txt/sta* format, see Figures 54-55:

- Select the operation with new data in *sta* file adding the action type in the column *command*: *add* (new station), *overwrite* (new station data), *remove* (delete station), *none* (ignore new data), See Figure 55.

The water use data is upgraded the same way as monthly point source data in the *waterUseMonthly.txt* and *sta* files and is loaded during creation of the catchments.

Figure 53: Workflow for updating monthly (upper) and small (lower) point source data.

id	year	name	type	nutrient	concentration	unit	discharge	y	x				
1	1999	110004884	Uzdaroji	akcine	bendrove	VILLON	311	BOD7	14.8	mgO2/l	23	6077488	572499
2	2000	110004884	Uzdaroji	akcine	bendrove	VILLON	311	BOD7	10.83	mgO2/l	26.8	6084863	491913
3	2001	110004884	Uzdaroji	akcine	bendrove	VILLON	311	BOD7	8.58	mgO2/l	28.8	6077488	572499
4	2002	110004884	Uzdaroji	akcine	bendrove	VILLON	311	BOD7	9.33	mgO2/l	28.9	6077494	4
5	2003	110004884	Uzdaroji	akcine	bendrove	VILLON	311	BOD7	7.15	mgO2/l	24	6077488	572499

Figure 54: Pointsource pollution data file *monthly.txt*.

ID	WWTP	X	Y	textID	command
1	311	572499	6077488	110004884	Uzdaroji.akcine.bendrove.VILLON

Figure 55: Pointsource file *monthly.sta*.

4. Landuse

Data sources for the land use update are Crops_Data, Forest_cadaster, Abandoned land, GDR topographic map and Geoland imperviousness. The workflow for land use update is shown in Figure 56:

- Preparing the union file according to description in PAIC (2021), Section 3.2.2.
- Importing union file in the *postgre* database

Figure 56: Workflow for updating land use and soil data.

5. Fertilization data

There are several methods for changing/updating fertilization data:

- Using the dedicated scripts for updating fertilization data, see Sections 3.1.7-3.1.9 of PAIC (2022). Note that these scripts will update the fertilization data if the inputs are updated (planned yields, animal data, the values relating base assumptions).
- Editing the relevant data as described in Section 3.2.7 of PAIC (2021):
 - a. planned yield data and declared crop database
 - b. animal data and farm animal numbers

6. Atmospheric deposition data

Script to convert atmospheric deposition data and links for data source is located in *Data\AtmosphericDeposition*. The description of Atmospheric deposition data is given in Section 3.2.4 of PAIC (2021).

7.2.2. Running scripts for implementing measures

Instructions for running the scripts for implementation of water quality improvement measures are provided with the script description in Section 3.1 of PAIC (2022) and Chapter 3 of this report. In this Section we outline the logics for the use of scripts.

1. Base parameters

For all HRU level scripts we should specify the scope (or base) of HRUs affected by the measure:

- Watershed list defines the scope of watersheds affected by the measure
- Application fraction defines to which part of HRU we apply the measure. Fraction application types are:
 - First: application to the first HRU from the list.
 - Shuffle: application to the random HRU from the list.
 - Split: each affected HRU is split in two.
- Landuse types defines the scope of landuses affected by the measure.
- Soil types defines the scope of soils affected by the measure.

2. Point source change

For doing scenario runs after the main calculations, i.e. introducing hypothetical scenarios including removing or editing existing point sources or adding new ones, user may change or add point sources and/or data (loads) from these point sources. Monthly and yearly sources and data are handled separately.

3. Landuse conversion by landuse groups

This measure is used for changing landuse groups to implement general forestation, general urbanization etc. User should define

- Base parameters defining the scope of HRUs for measure application (see point 1 above)

- Conversion of one landuse group to another (which group should be changed to what group):
 - groupCodeAgriculture = "AGRICULTURAL"
 - groupCodePasture = "PASTURE"
 - groupCodeForest = "FOREST"
 - groupCodeUrban = "URBAN"
 - groupCodeWetland = "WETLAND"
 - groupCodeBarren="BARREN"
 - groupCodeWater="WATER"

4. Landuse conversion by landuse code

This measure is used for changing landuse groups to implement general forestation, general urbanization etc. User should define

- Base parameters defining the scope of HRUs for measure application (see point 1 above)
- Conversion of one landuse code to another (which code should be changed to what code). Codes should be changed one by one.

5. Catch crops

For implementing the catch crops user should define

- Base parameters
- Additional "catch crops" for combining with HRU's crops, possible catch crops are crops:
 - a. RYE - Winter rye
 - b. WBAR - Winter barley
 - c. WTRC - Winter triticale
 - d. WWHT - Winter Wheat
- Plant passports for catch crops are in table *measures.plantmng_catchcrops*

6. Planting of winter crops

For implementing the planting of winter crops user should define

- Base parameters
- Select the crop for replacement with winter crop

The eligible crops for replacement with winter crops are

AGRC - Agricultural land	BARL - Summer barley
BWHT – Buckwheat	CANP - Annual grasses
CELR – Caraway	CORN - Corn
CRRT – Vegetables	CSIL - Corn for silage
GRBN – Beans/annual legumes	LMIX - Mix of legumes with other crops
LUPN – Lupine	OATS - Oats
PEAS – Peas	POTA - Potatoes
SCAN - Summer rape	SGBT - Sugar beet
SOYB – Soy	STBR - Summer barley (straw fields)
STCN - Summer rape (straw fields)	STRC - Summer triticale+summer rye
STWH - Summer wheat (straw fields)	
SWHT - Summer wheat	VTCH – Vetch

The possible winter crops can be found in the postgre table *measures.luclass_plantingofwintercrops*. By default winter crop is set to RYE.

7. Plant cover in winter

This measure implements leaving the plant cover during winter and it is applicable mostly for the summer crops:

AGRC - Agricultural land	BARL - Summer barley	BWHT – Buckwheat
CANP - Annual grasses	CELR -Caraway	CORN - Corn
CSIL - Corn for silage	LUPN – Lupine	OATS - Oats
SCAN - Summer rape	SOYB - Soy	
STBR - Summer barley (straw fields)		
STCN - Summer rape (straw fields)		
STRC - Summer triticale+summer rye		
STWH - Summer wheat (straw fields)		
SWHT - Summer wheat	VTCH - Vetch	

8. No-plough technology

This measure replaces deep ploughing with stubble breaking. The measure is applicable to:

BARL - Summer barley	BWHT – Buckwheat	CANP - Annual grasses
CELR – Caraway	CORN – Corn	CSIL - Corn for silage
LUPN – Lupine	OATS – Oats	SCAN - Summer rape
SOYB – Soy	SWHT - Summer wheat	
VTCH – Vetch	CANA - Winter rape	RYE - Rye
WBAR - Winter barley	WTRC - Winter triticale	
WWHT - Winter wheat		

9. Substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing

Substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing is applicable to sandy and medium to heavy soils (Table 6) and specific crops (Table 7).

10. Postponing a sod ploughing to late autumn

Postponing a sod ploughing to late autumn is applicable only for sandy soils and specific crops:

BARL - Summer barley	LUPN – Lupine	BWHT - Buckwheat
OATS – Oats	CANP - Annual grasses	SCAN - Summer rape
CELR – Caraway	SOYB – Soy	CORN - Corn
SWHT - Summer wheat	CSIL - Corn for silage	VTCH - Vetch

11. Fertilization amount

This measure gives the possibility of changing fertilizer amounts. The following parameters are introduced to steer the measure:

- fertCoef – multiplies all application of manure and fertilization

- fertCoefN - multiplies the amount of nitrogen to be applied
- fertCoefP - multiplies the amount of phosphorus to be applied
- FertMaxN - limits the maximum amount of nitrogen applied
- FertMaxP - limits the maximum amount of phosphorus applied
- FertMaxManure – limits the maximal amount of manure applied

Table 6: Soils eligible for substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing.

Soil	L/S	Soil	L/S	Soil	L/S	Soil	L/S
ADb-g4	L	GLn1	S	Jlb2	S	RDg4-k2	S
ADb-g5	L	GLv-k	S	Jlb2-e1	S	RDg8-k1	S
ADb-y	S	GLv-p	S	Jlb2-e2	S	RDg8-k2	S
ADb2	L	GLv-s	L	Jlg8-b	S	RDk1	S
ADd-p	L	IDg4-k	S	Jlg8-n	S	RDk1-e1	S
ADk-g4	L	IDg4-n1	S	Jln-g0	S	RDk1-g0	S
ADk-g5	L	IDg4-p	S	Jln2	S	RDk2	S
ADk-p	L	IDg8-k	S	PDa2	L	RDk2-e1	S
ADk-s	L	IDg8-n1	S	PDa2-(n)	L	RDk2-g0	S
ADn-g4	L	IDg8-p	S	PDt1	L	SDg4-b	L
ADn-g5	L	IDk-g0	S	PDt2	L	SDg4-n	L
ADn1	L	IDk-p	S	PDt2-(n)	L	SDg8-b	L
ADv-p	L	IDk-p-e1	S	PDz1	L	SDg8-k	L
ADv-u	L	IDk-p-e2	S	PDz2	L	SDg8-n	L
GLb-y	S	IDp-n1	S	PDz2-(n)	L	SDk-p	L
GLb-s	L	IDp-n1-g0	S	PLb-g4	S	SDp-b	L
GLb2	S	IDp-t	S	PLb2	S	SDp-b-e2	L
GLd-p	S	IDp-t-e1	S	PLn-g4	L	SDp-b-g0	L
GLd-s	L	IDp-t-e2	S	PLn1	L	SDp-n	L
GLk-s	L	IDp-t-g0	S	PRb2	S	SDp-n-g0	L
GLk1	S	JDg8-t	S	PRk-p-(e3)	S		
GLk2	S	Jlb-g0	S	RDb2	S		

Table 7: Crops eligible for substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing.

AGRC	Agricultural land	LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
ALFA	Perennial legumes	LUPN	Lupine
BARL	Summer barley	OATS	Oats
BWHT	Buckwheat	PEAS	Peas
CANP	Annual grasses	POTA	Potatoes
CELR	Caraway	SCAN	Summer rape
CORN	Corn	SGBT	Sugar beet
CRRT	Vegetables	SOYB	Soy
CSIL	Corn for silage	SWHT	Summer wheat
GRBN	Beans/ annual legumes	VTCH	Vetch

12. Fertilization timing

The measures changes the timing of fertilization. Parameters of how to change the timing is defined in PostgreSQL database table *plantmng_fertilizertiming*.

13. Fertilization technique

This measure allows changing the application technique of fertilizers from the default technique *inject* as well as fertilizer amount. The measure is applicable only for agricultural HRUs. Its input parameters are

- *Fertilizesettings* – fertilization amount as in the change of fertilizer amount, see point 11 above.
- *ApplicationType* – select method of application from *drill*, *broadcast*, *band*, *foliar*, *inject*, *aerial_liquid*, *aerial_solid*, *side_dress*, *fertigate*, *basal*, *rope_wick*, *tree_inject*.

14. Grassed waterways

Grassed waterways measure allows introduction of grassed waterways. User shall provide *Grassedwaterway* parameter which contains all parameters to define grassed waterways in HRUs:

- *mann* - Mannings's n for grassed waterway (default 0.05)
- *sed_co* - sediment transport coefficient defined by user (default 0.02)
- *dp* - depth of grassed waterway (m) (default 0.75)
- *wd* - width of grass waterway (m) (default 3)
- *len* - length of Grass Waterway (km) (default 0.75)
- *slp* - slope of grass waterway (m/m) (default 0.035)

15. Filter strips

Filter strips measure allows the introduction of filter strips (overwriting existing set of filter strips). User shall provide *Filterstrip* parameter containing the values for HRU level implementation:

- *fld_vfs* - Ratio of field area to filter strip area
- *con_vfs* - Fraction of flow entering the most concentrated 10% of the filterstrip
- *cha_q* - Fraction of fully channelized flow

16. Managed drainage

Managed drainage measure allows introducing the tile drains (overwriting existing drain parameters). User shall provide *Tiledrain* parameter that contains all necessary parameters for tile drains:

- *dp* - Depth of drain tube from the soil surface (mm);
- *t_fc* - Time to drain soil to field capacity (hr);
- *lag* - Drain tile lag time (hr);
- *rad* - Effective radius of drains (mm);
- *dist* - Distance between two drain tubes or tiles (mm);
- *drain* - Drainage coefficient (mm/day);
- *pump* - Pump capacity (mm/hour);
- *lat_ksat* - Multiplication factor to determine lateral *ksat* from SWAT *ksat* input value.

17. Sedimentation ponds and wetlands

Sedimentation ponds and wetlands is a catchment level measure which introduces a wetland object. It is applicable for Agricultural, Pasture, Forest and Urban landuse groups. User shall provide *Landuse_to_wetland* – dictionary containing SWAT+ wetland parameters.

18. Pesticides

The measure is aimed for adding pesticides in plant management. User shall provide *Measures.plantmg_pesticides* – a table for defining what pesticide is used for specific crop.

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